

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: DENNIE****FIRST NAME: REBEKAH****PROGRAM CODE: DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 7%

The author used the following software: Microsoft 365 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What are the components of the dissertation research process, and what is the order of progression?

- Dissertation concept paper, Dissertation Prospectus, Dissertation, and Dissertation Manuscript.¹**
- Dissertation and Dissertation Prospectus.
- Dissertation Manuscript, Dissertation concept paper, and Dissertation.
- Dissertation and Dissertation Manuscript.

¹ James P. Sampson Jr., *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd Edition (Tallahassee, Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 9.

2. What are the components of a scholarly research argument, and what is the order of progression?

Claim, Reason, Evidence, Acknowledgement and Response, Warrant.²

Evidence, Reason, Warrant.

Reason, Acknowledgment and Response, Claim, Evidence.

Warrant, Claim, Reason, Acknowledgement and Response, Evidence.

3. Knowing when to quote, paraphrase, and summarize another author's work is essential.

Which author said:

Summarize when details are irrelevant or a source isn't important enough to warrant much space.

Paraphrase when you can state what a source says more clearly or concisely or when your argument depends on the details in a source but not on its specific words.

- Quote for these purposes:
- The words themselves are evidence that backs up your reasons.
- The words are from an authority who backs up your claims.
- The words are strikingly original or express your key concepts so compellingly that the quotation can frame an extended discussion.
- The words express a claim you disagree with, and to be fair you want to state it exactly.

(Turabian et al. 2018, 77).³

(Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, 77).

² Kate L. Turabian, Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 9th Edition (Chicago, London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

³ Ibid., 77.

- (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 77).
- (Sampson, Jr. 2017, 77).

4. What are the two citation styles, and what is their difference?

- Note bibliography style is used to identify that you have used a source by putting a superscript number at the end of the sentence in which you quote it or refer to it, and Author-date style is used to identify that you have used a source by putting parenthetical citation (including author, date and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it.⁴**
- Simply Notes Style is a shortened note of an author's work; date style is citing an author's work by referencing the publication date only.
- Note bibliography style is where the reference is stated in parentheses, and author style is when the author's name is stated in parentheses to reference their work.
- Bibliography style refers to the reference style used in the bibliography section of a research paper, and author-date style refers to referencing the publications, date of the author's work, and their full name.

5. How are sources in the bibliography section arranged when the same author wrote more than one article/book/publication and the like?

- They are arranged alphabetically based on the title of the book (but "a" and "the" are not assessed in the process). After the first source by an author is**

⁴ Ibid., 141-142.

placed in the bibliography section, the author's name in the subsequent references is replaced by a long dash.⁵

- They are arranged alphabetically based on the title of the book.
 - They are arranged alphabetically based on the date of the publication. After the first source by an author is placed in the bibliography section, the author's name in the subsequent references is replaced by a 3-em dash.
 - There is no particular format; most importantly, individual sources are referenced using a scholarly referencing style.
6. Which author highlighted the importance of having an aesthetically and technically pleasing research topic, and what key characteristics should a topic have?
- A research topic should consists of two parts, the main topic and the sub-topic that highlight a key element of the research. (Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, 713–14).⁶**
 - A research topic should be captivating, but limited to eight words, not including a/an/and/the (Turabian et al. 2018, 50).
 - A research topic should accurately represent the theme of the research (European Commission 2016, 15).
 - A research topic should be grammatically sound and include appropriate punctuations (Turabian et al. 2018, 34).

⁵ Ibid., 156.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End, 4th Edition* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 173-174.

7. Which option most accurately represent a process and or goal of conducting a literature review.

"Identify key theories, or concepts related to the phenomenon and/or context under study, and which of these will most appropriately frame and situate your study" (Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, 353).⁷

"Identify key theories, or concepts related to the phenomenon" (Bloomberg and Volpe 2019, 353).

A literature review should only highlight theories that are related to the topic.

Only the most relevant research should be included in the literature review.

8. What are the two ways to identify a journal article reference?

The word "journal" may be found in the title of the document and a DOI indicates it's a journal document.⁸

The presence of a DIO indicates it is journal article.

All journal articles must state it's a journal in the title.

The word journal must be in the title and a DOI is an indicator of a journal document.

9. What are the elements of a publication and how do they differ in a note and bibliography entries?

⁷ Ibid., 353.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 189-190.

- The elements are the place (city) of publication, the publisher's name, and the publication date (year). In notes, this information is placed within parentheses; in the bibliography, they are not.**⁹
- The elements are the publisher's name and the date of publication. Moreover, there is no difference between notes and bibliography entries.
- The elements are the place of publication and the date of publication. Moreover, both entries are placed within parentheses.
- The elements are the place of publication, the publisher's name, and the publication date. Furthermore, both entries do not require parentheses.

10. What punctuation are used to separate elements in the notes and bibliography entries?

- A comma separates most components of notes, whereas bibliography entries are separated by a period.**¹⁰
- A comma separates most components of notes and bibliography entries.
- A comma separates most components of a bibliography entry, whereas note entries are separated by a period.
- Most components of notes and bibliography entries are separated by periods.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

⁹ Ibid., 181.

¹⁰ Ibid., 154.

James Sampson, Jr. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

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